

**DYNAMICS OF ANTHROPOMETRIC INDICATORS IN THE
DEVELOPMENT OF ONE-YEAR-OLD CHILDREN****(2024 in the case of the city of Urganch)****Yuldashev Bakhrom Sabirjanevich ¹, Karimov Rasulbek Khasanovich ²,
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Relevance of the topic: Each infancy period of childhood is characterized by biological characteristics and helps to achieve adequate morphofunctional development at the next stage, if the natural nutrition of children is not artificially reduced. In the first year of children's life, that is, in the neonatal and breastfeeding age, the necessary conditions for adaptation to the microsocial environment, neuropsychological, and somatic conditions are formed. In general, in the first year of life, children are characterized by a faster rate of physical development, interdependence of neuropsychic and physical development, resistance to weather and environmental conditions, defects in care and nutrition than in older children.

Purpose of work: as the purpose of the work, children under one year living in Urganch city and Khazarasp district of Khorezm region were examined in family polyclinics in their place of residence.

The obtained results: 200 of the 536 children under one year of age involved in the investigation are from the city of Urganch, 336 of them are from Khazarasp district, 160 of the children under one year of age live in the city of Urganch. It was found that 176 of them are boys and 176 are girls, 112 of the children under one year of age living in Khazarasp district are boys, 88 are girls, and most of the children are fed artificial food rather than breast milk.

Conclusions: in the conclusion, it can be said that when the statistical, anamnestic and anthropometric dimensions of children under 1 year old fed with artificial and natural food are measured, the body structure of children fed with natural food is correct, their mind and clear and fluent answers to questions, visible mucous membranes are well developed, that anthropometric dimensions are normal,

if no defects were found in the locomotor system, it was found that formula-fed children were slightly behind their peers in terms of intelligence, the length of their left leg was longer than the right leg, their visible mucous membranes were not well developed, and their body growth was slightly behind their age peers. .

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